

SUBSTANTIATION OF THE ADVANTAGE OF USING PLATELET-RICH FIBRIN IN THE TREATMENT OF JAW CYSTS

Mirzakulova Lola Tokhirovna

Assistant department of Stomatology, Zarmed University, Uzbekistan

E-mail: mirzakulovalola42@gmail.com

Mardonova Nigora Parda kizi

Assistant department of Stomatology, Samarkand State Medical
University, Uzbekistan

Orcid: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14769989>

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19333824>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 21st March 2026

Accepted: 25th March 2026

Online: 30th March 2026

KEYWORDS

*hypoallergenic, follicular,
radicular, paradental, platelet,
autoplasma, hyperemia*

ABSTRACT

This article presents research studies to substantiate the advantages of using platelet-rich fibrin in the treatment of maxillary cysts. It discusses the various characteristics of maxillary cysts, including radicular, follicular, paradental, and epidermoid cysts, the problems of treating their pathological processes, the use of surgical procedures in treatment, complications, and the achievement of optimal treatment measures for the disease based on analysis and data.

Introduction. Relevance of the topic. According to the data of Candidate of Medical Sciences Igor Aleksandrovich Kuzminykh, in outpatient surgical dental practice, radicular cysts account for 78-96% of the total number of jaw cysts and 7-12% of all jaw diseases. Maxillofacial surgeon and dental surgeon Alexey Timofeev, analyzing his clinical observations, found that among 1,000 patients with jaw cysts, 85% were radicular cysts, 9% follicular, 3% paradental, and 1% epidermoid cysts.

On the one hand, these figures demonstrate the relevance of the problem of treating this pathology. On the other hand, surgical interventions performed to treat cysts lead to a disruption of bone integrity, and its restoration requires a long period of time. Prolonged healing, in turn, may result in defective regeneration of bone tissue. For this reason, reducing the duration of the postoperative healing period represents another important aspect of the relevance of this topic.

The specific features of using methods to optimize osteogenesis lie in the fact that they exhibit their beneficial effects at certain stages of bone regeneration. Therefore, the use of platelet-rich autoplasm is intended to reduce inflammatory reactions in tissues and to create favorable conditions for bone formation by effectively influencing the mechanisms of osteogenesis.

The purpose of the study. Improvement of the surgical method of treatment with the use of platelet-rich fibrin in the reconstruction of the jaw bone defect in odontogenic cysts.

Research material and methods. In our study, patients were divided into two groups, group 1 was conventional, and group 2 was treated with PRF during cystectomy. The

abbreviation PRF is taken from the English language and means "Platelltes Reach Fibrin". Platelet-rich fibrin is a therapeutic method that facilitates the postoperative and rehabilitation period, increases the effectiveness of surgical intervention. There are two types of PRF, A-PRF and I-PRF, both types are used in surgical dentistry. A-PRF is widely used mainly in the treatment of jaw cysts. Platelet-rich fibrin is safe, natural, hypoallergenic, atraumatic, and its effect on reducing the rehabilitation period has been clinically proven. PRF is taken directly in the clinic. During the admission, blood is taken from the patient's vein into a special test tube according to a special protocol and placed in a centrifuge. The formation of PRF in a centrifuge depends on its type. For A- PRF, the maximum speed is set to 1300 rpm for a maximum of 8 minutes. For I- PRF, the maximum speed is set to 700 rpm for a maximum of 3 minutes. Then, depending on the material of the test tube, it is left in the centrifuge for 7 to 10 minutes. Test tubes made of glass take longer to form than test tubes made of plastic.

Research methods. Experimental research. The experimental part of the scientific research. The Ministry of Health of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent State Dental Institute named after Academician K.A.Zufarov, was carried out in collaboration with the staff of the department in the laboratory of the Department of "Histology and Medical Biology". Conducting research on animals made it possible to morphologically assess the speed and quality of the osteoreparation process, monitor it in dynamics, identify possible complications and confirm contraindications to the use of this drug. Thus, the parallel conduct of the experimental part along with clinical research and testing is considered the main and integral part of the scientific work. The study achieved a dynamic study of the process of reparative osteogenesis in cases where an artificial bone defect was created in the jaw bones of rabbits with and without the use of the osteoplastic material "A-oss". According to the results of the conducted morphological examinations, a mutual comparison of the osteoplastic material "A-oss" and the process of bone regeneration in the blood clot in the area of the created defect was checked. In order to morphologically evaluate the dynamics of bone tissue recovery and to determine the effect of osteoplastic material on the recovery of a bone defect, the method of artificially creating a defect in the lower jaw of rabbits was used.

Experimental. In order to evaluate the post-operative condition of rabbits in both groups, a diary was kept to record the local and general condition indicators.

- *Level of activity in mobility:* active mobility, partially active mobility, slow mobility, low mobility;
- *Level of nutrition:* normal appetite, satisfactory appetite, decreased appetite, refusal to eat;
- *Fluid intake:* moderate, reduced, minimal fluid intake, fluid rejection;
- *Body temperature;*
- *Condition of wound sutures:* satisfactory, unsatisfactory;
- *Edema in the wound area:* absence of edema, imperceptible edema, partial edema, diffuse edema;
- *Hyperemia:* Redness of the operative wound area, absence of redness;
- *Painfulness (on palpation)* pain is observed, not observed;
- *Indicator of wound healing:* primary healing, secondary healing.

Results of experimental studies. The condition of the animals was monitored during the experiment, from the day of the experiment to the 14th day. The clinical results of the experiment were evaluated according to the following criteria: movement activity, food intake, fluid intake, body temperature, suture position, swelling, hyperemia, pain during palpation, body weight.

The level of activity in mobility: 1-active mobility, 2-partially active mobility, 3- slow mobility, 4- low mobility;

Level of nutrition: 1-normal appetite, 2-satisfied appetite, 3-reduction of appetite, 4-rejection of nutrition;

Fluid intake: 1-moderate, 2-reduced, 3-minimum fluid intake, 3-rejection of fluid;

Condition of wound sutures: 1-satisfactory, 2-unsatisfactory;

Swelling in the area of the wound: 1 no swelling, 2-symptomatic swelling, 3-partial swelling, 4 diffuse swelling;

Hyperemia: 1- Redness of the operative wound area, 2- Absence of redness;

Pain (on palpation) 1st pain is observed, 2nd is not observed;

Wound healing index: 1st primary healing, 2nd secondary healing.

Results of morphological examination. On the 7th day of the experiment, the morphological study of the dynamics of reparative regeneration of bone tissue in the area of the artificially created defect in the mandible in the animals of the control group showed that an infiltrate rich in connective tissue cells was detected in the place of the blood clot in the area of the defect. During this period, the main group observed the rapid growth of blood vessels from the surrounding bone tissue to the wound site.

Conclusion. In patients undergoing cystectomy in the area of the defect formed after the operation of the odontogenic cyst of the jaw bone using the biological material PRF, the densitometric index in the defect area was 40 ± 5 on the 1st day after the operation, 45 ± 5 on the 1st month after the operation, 55 ± 5 on the 3rd month after the operation, 65 ± 5 on the 6th month after the operation, and 75 ± 5 on the 12th month after the operation. However, when using the biological material PRF that we propose, the densitometric index in the defect area was 50 ± 5 on the 1st day after the operation, 70 ± 5 on the 1st month after the operation, 90 ± 5 on the 3rd month after the operation, 110 ± 5 on the 6th month after the operation, and 160 ± 5 on the 12th month after the operation.

List of references:

- 1.Ибрагимов, Д.Д., Мардонова, Н.П., Исмаатов, Н.С., & Кучкоров, Ф.Ш. (2023). Жағ кисталарини даволашда тромбоцитлар билан тўйинган фибриннинг қўллаш авзаллиги. MedUnion, 2(1), 88-93.
2. Марданова Н.П., Кудратова Н.Б., Фарходов Ё.Ф. Оптимизация исходов хирургической терапии одонтогенных кист челюстных костей //Состав редакционной коллегии и организационного комитета: Аймурзина Б.Т, доктор экономических наук Ахмедова НР, доктор искусствоведения Базарбаева СМ, доктор технических наук Битокова СХ, доктор филологических наук. – 2024.)
3. Ибрагимов, Д., Гаффаров, У., & Марданова, Н. Редкий случай удаления крупного слюнного камня при хроническом калькулёзном сиаладените. Международный центр научного партнерства «Новая Наука» (ИП Ивановская ИИ) Конференция:

Ломоносовские чтения. Актуальные вопросы фундаментальных и прикладных исследований Петрозаводск, 01 апреля 2024

4. Мардонова, Н., Юлдашев, Н., Каттахонов, Ж., & Каримов, Х. Повышение эффективности хирургического лечения одонтогенных кист челюстей. Международный центр научного партнерства «Новая Наука» (ИП Ивановская ИИ) Конференция: наука. Образование. Технологии: тенденции современного развития Петрозаводск, 08 января 2024 года Организаторы: Международный центр научного партнерства «Новая Наука» (ИП Ивановская ИИ).

5. Шодиев, С.С., Исматов, Ф.А., Нарзиева, Д.Б., Тухтамишев, Н.О., & Ахмедов, Б.С. (2019). Эффективность применения отвара аниса при лечении периимплантитов. Достижения науки и образования, (11 (52)), 99-103.

6. Исматов, Ф.А., Мустафоев, А.А., & Фуркатов, Ш.Ф. (2023). Анализ эффективности нестероидных противовоспалительных препаратов при излеченье верхнечелюстного альвеолита. Theory and analytical aspects of recent research, 1(12), 49-57.

7. Исматов, Ф.А., Шодиев, С. С., & Мусурманов, Ф.И. (2020). Анализ изучения стоматологического и общего здоровья студентов вузов города самарканда. Биомедицина ва амалиёт журналы, (6), 34-39.

8. Хасанова, Л.Э., & Исматов, Ф.А. (2020). Комплексная социально-гигиеническая характеристика условий, образа жизни и здоровья студентов. преимущества обследования студенческой молодежи. Проблемы биологии и медицины, 1, 286-293.

9. Ismatov, F.A. (2022). Abdullaev T.Z methods of application of single-stage dental implants for different degrees of alveolar atrophy. Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal, 3(8), 636-643.

10. Aslidinovich, I.F., & Abdurasulovich, M.A. (2022). Structure of single-stage dental implants for varying degrees of alveolar atrophy. World Bulletin of Public Health, 10, 156-159.

11. Ismatov, F.A. (2020). Comparative tender characteristics of student dental Health indexes. ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research, (10), 11.

12. Ismatov, F.A. (2023). Evaluation of the efficacy of alendronic acid in dental implantation (literature review). American Journal of Pediatric Medicine and Health Sciences (2993 2149), 1(7), 199-202.

13. Aslidinovich, I.F. (2023). Assessment of the Effectiveness of Alendronic Acid in Dental Implants. Central Asian Journal of Medical and Natural Science, 4(3), 1186-1188.

14. Khasanova, L.E., & Ismatov, F.A. (2022). Indicators of oral health at students of the city of samarkand. Applied Information Aspects of Medicine (Prikladnye informacionnye aspekty mediciny), 25(4), 13-19.

15. Ismatov, F.A., & Mustafoyev, A.A. (2022). Drug treatment with non-steroidal anti inflammatory drugs jaw alveolitis. Frontline Medical Sciences and Pharmaceutical Journal, 2(03), 88-94.

16. Хасанов, Х.Ш., Исматов, Ф.А., & Мардонова, Н.П. (2022). Применение " prf" в качестве остеопластического материала при одонтогенных кистах челюстных костей. Вестник магистратуры, (2-1 (125)), 13-14.